
EVALUATION OF ANTERIOR SEGMENT IMAGING TECHNIQUES IN DIAGNOSIS OF KERATOCONUS

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Abstract:

Keratoconus, which was first described in detail in 1854 (derived from the Greek terms *kerato*, meaning cornea, and *konos* meaning cone) is a bilateral, noninflammatory,¹ progressive disorder characterized by corneal ectasia, thinning, protrusion and asymmetric corneal degenerative disease that compromises the structural integrity of the collagen matrix within the corneal stroma. The hallmark characteristic is the development of a localized, cone-shaped ectasia (bulge or hernia) that is accompanied by thinning of the stroma in the area of the cone.^{2,3}

The diagnosis of more advanced keratoconus is not complicated, because of the typical biomicroscopic and topographic findings, but the detection of subclinical or forme fruste cases may impose difficulty. Currently the diagnosis of keratoconus is based on biomicroscopic findings, corneal topography and ultrasound pachymetry. Placido-disk based corneal topography only examines the anterior surface of the cornea and alteration in the reference point or viewing angle may result in inaccuracy of curvature measurement. Corneal thickness is a valuable indicator of the health and physiology of the cornea. For instance, Central corneal thickness is essential information in situations where the cornea is thinned, either pathologically as in the case of Keratoconus or intentionally via refractive surgery. In refractive surgery, central corneal thickness is a crucial determinant of the amount of treatment that needs to occur for the desired refractive outcome and also for the avoidance of postoperative keratorefractive complications (Fakhry, Artola et al. 2002).^{6,7}

The goal of the present study is to compare central corneal thickness measurements and corneal curvature from three instruments in corneas that have been thinned due to keratoconus. Because each instrument is based on different principles, measurements can be biased when measured in abnormally thin corneas.

The purpose of our study was to diagnose the cases of Keratoconus with the help of Pentacam, Corneal topography and Ultrasound pachymetry and to compare the efficiency of these three methods for the diagnosis of Keratoconus.

Keywords: *Keratoconus, Pentacam, Ultrasound Pachymetry, Corneal Topography.*

INTRODUCTION:

Forme fruste Keratoconus, or subclinical Keratoconus, is an early form of the disease that does not affect the patients best spectacle corrected visual acuity, and does not present evidence of progression. Forme fruste Keratoconus was first described by Amsler.¹¹ It is essentially an extremely mild form of Keratoconus that manifests as a central or para central zone of irregular astigmatism. By definition, forme fruste of Keratoconus is characterized by the lack of progression, having as a result the absence of diagnosis, if no special examinations such as corneal topography are undertaken. Forme fruste of Keratoconus is a contraindication for LASIK surgery and the diagnosis is very important in refractive surgery candidates.

Corneal thickness is a valuable indicator of the health and physiology of the cornea. Specifically, central corneal thickness (CCT) measurements are vitally important for the diagnosis, treatment, and management of various ocular conditions. For instance, Central corneal thickness is essential information in situations where the cornea is thinned, either pathologically as in the case of Keratoconus or intentionally via refractive surgery. In refractive surgery, central corneal thickness is a crucial determinant of the amount of treatment that needs to occur for the desired refractive outcome and also for the avoidance of postoperative keratorefractive complications.^{8,9}

Ultrasound pachymetry requires the use of topical anaesthetic and contact with the cornea. It is based on the reflection of sound from the anterior and posterior corneal surfaces although the exact posterior corneal reflection point for ultrasound waves is not known (Ehlers, Shah et al. 2008).^{8,9}

The Pentacam Comprehensive Eye Scanner uses a rotating Scheimpflug camera and measures both anterior and posterior corneal surfaces by an elevation based system.⁴ It allows the measurement of local elevation points by fitting the corneal shape to a best fit sphere reference surface with variable diameters or to an ellipsoid surface. Examination of the posterior corneal surface is important in the early diagnosis of keratoconus as epithelial compensation can mask the presence of an underlying cone on the anterior surface.¹¹

MAPPING KERATOCONUS BY PENTACAM:

The posterior surface of the cornea usually reveals the first detectable thinning, and protrusion of this surface. Nevertheless, the back surface of the cornea is never as precise as the front, because its curvature and height are calculated by looking through the front surface of the cornea, making the back surface a virtual image.

In Keratoconus, the sagittal or tangential map, pachymetry map, and posterior elevation map all show the same “hot spot” point. A hot spot in the same location on all three maps indicates an irregularity such as a Keratoconus.

Screenings for Keratoconus are as follows:

Anterior and posterior elevation maps: In the anterior elevation map differences between the best fit sphere and the corneal contour of less than +12 μ m are considered normal, between +12 μ m and +15 μ m are suspicious, and more than +15 μ m are typically considered as keratoconus. Similar numbers about 5 μ m higher apply to posterior elevation maps.

Anterior curvature map: The steepening of the cornea, irregular astigmatism, inferior steepening (I – S difference), location of steepest point and the thinnest point on the cornea may help in the diagnosis of keratoconus.

Elevation-based topography offers important advances over Placido-disc based devices. The ability to image the posterior cornea and to produce an accurate pachymetric map is itself significant. Elevation subtraction maps are also more accurate in determining the cone morphology and in separating the false-positive keratoconus suspect cases.

The incidence and prevalence of keratoconus in the general population has been estimated to be between 5 and 23, and 5.4 per 10,000, respectively. A low incidence of the disease is apparent in Japan, Taiwan, and Singapore (Khoo 1989; Chen et al., 2001), Mediterranean and Middle Eastern areas appear to demonstrate high incidence and an increased manifestation (Totan et al., 2001; Tabbara, 1999).^{3,6}

BRIEF REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

1. In the study done by Saad A, Gatinel D, The mean +/- SD of highest rate of steepening was 3.60 +/- 1.70 D/mm (range 1.59 to 7.53 D/mm) in the clinically obvious keratoconus group, 1.59 +/- 0.21 D/mm (range 1.35 to 1.98 D/mm) in the keratoconus suspect group, and 0.72 +/- 0.31 D/mm (range 0.18 to 1.63 D/mm) in normal eyes. There was a statistically insignificant difference in the means of highest rate of steepening in the Pentacam and corneal topography ($p > 0.05$). He concluded that the highest rate of steepening may be a useful measure for keratoconus screening with corneal topography.

2. Gherghel D, Hosking SL, Mantry S, Banerjee S, Naroo SA, Shah S. found that more than one third of subjects with KCN developed manifest KCN in the other eye over 8 years. These authors reported the mean central corneal thickness found with ultrasound pachymetry was higher i.e. $510 \pm 49.24\mu\text{m}$ and with Pentacam was $491 \pm 51.32\mu\text{m}$ which was slightly lesser, which co-relate with our study.

3. In another study, based on topographic maps from the Pentacam, Ucakhan et al stated that KCN should be highly suspected in eyes with anterior elevation greater than $15\mu\text{m}$ and posterior elevation greater than $20\mu\text{m}$, corneal thickness less than $500\mu\text{m}$. Subjects who had anterior elevation between 12 and $15\mu\text{m}$, posterior elevation between 15 and $20\mu\text{m}$ with a corresponding location of thinnest pachymetry point less than $500\mu\text{m}$ were diagnosed as KCN suspect, but reported that the Pentacam gives thinnest pachymetry at the apex of keratoconus than the ultrasound pachymetry, as the examiner was not aware of keratoconus apex.

METHODOLOGY:

RESEARCH DESIGN:

This is a prospective, randomized, hospital based, comparative study done to find the prevalence of keratoconus eyes at our centre within a period of 6 month and to compare the accuracy of Pentacam with Ultrasound pachymetry and corneal Topography in assessing corneal thickness (CT) and corneal curvature respectively, in 60 eyes of 30 patients diagnosed to have Keratoconus.

We have examined all 415 patients coming to Lasik centre. In all patients we did examination with all 3 instruments and all patients who showed Keratoconus characteristics were recruited

and further compared in detail by all three instruments. The eye evaluation for Keratoconus by Pentacam, Corneal topography and Pachymetry for each patient was achieved at a single session lasting approximately 30 minutes. We have measured average and steep corneal curvature both, because highest rate of steepening may be a useful measure for keratoconus screening.

OBJECTIVES:

The aim of this study was to diagnose the cases of Keratoconus with the help of Pentacam, Corneal topography and Ultrasound pachymetry and to compare the efficiency of these three methods for the diagnosis of Keratoconus.

1. To find the prevalence of keratoconus eyes at Lasik center.
2. To compare the results of Ultrasound Pachymeter (UP) and Oculus Pentacam Scheimpflug system in measuring central corneal thickness (CCT).
3. To compare the results of Oculus Pentacam Scheimpflug system and Corneal topography (TMS-1) in measuring corneal curvature.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

Both eyes of every patient have undergone a complete ophthalmologic evaluation. If all of the following conditions are satisfied, the patient is eligible for the study:

- Age: ≥ 10 as smaller children will not cooperate well with the instruments to 40 years as beyond this age the keratoconus will be in advanced stage and we are concerned in identifying mild to moderate stage.
- Irregular corneal surface in either eye determined by distortion of keratometric mires, of the Retinoscopic scissor reflex, or higher astigmatism in prescription.
- Either Vogt's striae in the deep stroma or Munson's sign or corneal scarring characteristic of keratoconus in either eye.
- No gender preference.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

If a patient has the following condition she/he is excluded from the Study:

- Age: below 10 years and above 40 years
- Bilateral corneal transplants.
- Non-keratoconic corneal disease in both eyes: Pellucid Marginal Degeneration, Terrien's Marginal Degeneration, Keratoglobus.

The clinical assessment routine for each patient included the following:

DEMOGRAPHIC DETAILS:

For identification of patients and statistical analysis¹⁰: history regarding name, age, gender, residence, occupation, case register no. was noted.

PRELIMINARY EXAMINATIONS:

In all patients visual acuity, refraction and slit lamp for anterior segment was evaluated. The participants were informed about the purpose of the study and gave informed consent before inclusion.

CORNEAL TOPOGRAPHIC MEASUREMENTS:

Corneal topographic measurements were taken with the Oculus corneal topographer (Oculus Easygraph Topographic Modeling System). The corneal topographer system consists of the topographer itself and a personal computer. The software is almost fully automated. After the patient's data were entered, the program changed to imaging mode. Briefly, the patients were instructed to place their chin in the chin rest and press their foreheads against the forehead straps, and asked to keep both eyes open and fixate on the target, in the centre of the red fixation beam. The image was then focused and centred manually by moving the joystick in the respective directions. Topographic images were taken at 5 to 6 seconds after a complete blink, when the tear film layer is the most stable.

PENTACAM MEASUREMENTS:^{13, 14}

All eyes were examined with the Pentacam (Oculus Inc.). The readings were taken as recommended in the instruction manual. The Pentacam system consists of the Pentacam itself and a personal computer. The software is almost fully automated. After the patient's data were entered, the program changed to imaging mode. Briefly, the patients were instructed to place their chin in the chin rest and press their foreheads against the forehead straps, and asked to keep both eyes open and fixate on the black target, in the centre of the blue fixation beam. The examiner sees a real-time image of the patient's eye on the computer screen. The image was then focused and centred manually by moving the Pentacam in the respective directions. Markings on the screen indicate the direction; the operator should move the joystick of the camera. As soon as the image is perfectly aligned, the patient was asked not to move and to keep his or her eye open, and the scan was started. After attaining perfect alignment, the instrument automatically capture 25 Scheimpflug images of anterior segment within 2 seconds. For each eye one high quality image was recorded.

ULTRASOUND PACHYMETRY:¹³

The cornea was then anaesthetized with topical 0.5% proparacaine and five readings were taken with Ultrasound pachymeter (Sonomed). The patients were instructed to look straight ahead and fixate on a target. The hand held probe was applied perpendicularly on the centre of the cornea under anaesthesia. All five pachymetry readings were carried out by one examiner. In all cases, the five measurements were used for further comparative analysis.¹⁴

In our study the following data were then exported to a Performa sheet: Keratometry values in the flat (K1) and steep (K2) meridian, corneal thickness at the centre (central pachymetry) and at the thinnest point of the cornea (minimal pachymetry) and the topographical Keratoconus classification Indices.

RESULTS:

In this prospective, randomized, hospital based and comparative study, 415 patients were examined within 6 months from which 30 patients with Keratoconus were detected.

The population included were 13(43.33%) males and 17(56.67%) females' subjects ranged from (11 to 40 years) with the mean age of 23.9 years \pm 5.7.

TABLE 1- GENDER DISTRIBUTION

Gender	No.	%
MALE	13	43.33
FEMALE	17	56.67
TOTAL	30	100

The incidence was about 7.22% and the prevalence rate was 43.33% i.e. higher at the age of 21 to 25 years who were diagnosed with Keratoconus.

TABLE 2- AGE DISTRIBUTION

Age	No.	%
11-15 YRS	1	3.33
16-20 YRS	7	23.33
21-25 YRS	13	43.33
26-30 YRS	6	20
31-35 YRS	1	3.33
36-40 YRS	2	6.67

In our study we found the p-value 0.0001 which is < 0.05 , i.e. statistically significant when testing with two different pachymetry instruments, at 5% level of significance and the mean central corneal thickness found with ultrasound pachymetry was $503 \pm 50.04\mu\text{m}$ and with Pentacam was $499 \pm 50.32\mu\text{m}$.

TABLE 3- MEAN CORNEAL THICKNESS IN 60 EYES

Instruments	Mean corneal thickness (μ)	P - Value
ULTRASOUND PACHYMETER	503 \pm 50.04 (S.D.)	0.0001
PENTACAM	50.32 (S.D.)	

Again, Ultrasound pachymetry was only able to detect 32 eyes with Keratoconus thus 28 eyes were under diagnosed from it while Pentacam was able to detect all 60 eyes of keratoconus.

TABLE 4 – NO. OF EYES DIAGNOSED KERATOCONUS ON PACHYMETRY FINDING

Instruments	No. of eyes	Percentage (%)
ULTRASOUND PACHYMETER	32	53.33
PENTACAM	60	100

Secondly, when measuring average and steep corneal curvature we found the p-value *0.768206* and *0.542775* which is > 0.05 respectively, thus the difference found is statistically insignificant when testing with two different corneal curvature measuring instruments, at 5% level of significance. Mean average and mean steep corneal curvature found with corneal topography was $45.82 \pm 2.92D$ and with Pentacam was $45.79 \pm 3.23D$ and $47.03 \pm 3.60D$ and with Pentacam was $46.96 \pm 3.88D$ respectively.

TABLE 5 – MEAN OF AVERAGE CORNEAL CURVATURE READINGS IN DIOPTRES

Instruments	MEAN of Avg. Corneal Curvature Reading (D)	P-Value
CORNEAL TOPOGRAPHY	45.82 ± 2.92 (S.D.)	0.768206
PENTACAM	45.79 ± 3.23 (S.D.)	

TABLE 6 – MEAN OF STEEP CORNEAL CURVATURE READINGS IN DIOPTRIS

Instruments	MEAN of Steep Corneal Curvature Reading (D)	P-Value
CORNEAL TOPOGRAPHY	47.03 ± 3.60 (S.D.)	0.542775
PENTACAM	46.96 ± 3.88 (S.D.)	

CONCLUSION:

Early diagnosis of KCN is an important clinical issue because the incidence being 7.22% which is higher within 6 month period. We also know that cross- linking can halt the progression of this ectatic disease. Instruments which diagnose Keratoconus at early stage can avoid relative blindness due to Keratoconus. By halting Keratoconus to go it into last stage, we can decrease the incidence of less success ratio with keratoplasty which is the last choice of treatment. From the above to diagnose the case of keratoconus and that to at an early stage out of three, Pentacam provides more accurate diagnosis than conventional corneal topography systems and ultrasound pachymetry.

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